

‘MENTAL HEALTH IN CRIMINAL TRIAL IN BANGLADESH’

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Abstract:

This paper will discuss how mental health and criminal justice system works intersectionally in Bangladesh by explaining the scope of insanity, International prospective and Bangladesh prospective of infinity defence, effect of insanity in before after and during trial, challenges of clamming the defence of insanity, legal Framework, Consequences of prisoners who felt mental issues in Jail and afterwards some recommendation with context of internationals.

1. Introduction:

In 2016 a mother Mahfuza jasmine killed her two child Aroni and Alvi and confessed to the murders after arrest. She said that she killed her both children for artistic activity instead of studying. The Doctor in this case confirmed that killing own children just because of not studying is a sign of mental disorder cause a prudent person can never kill her child for that specially the mothers¹.

Mental health in the criminal justice system are woefully one of the most overlooked and less discussed issue in Bangladesh². Around 28% of people in the world suffers various kind of mental defect as like depression, sleeping disorder, personality disorder etc and most of the Criminals approximately 60% typically suffer from a variety of mental disorders and they commit crime for their anti-social behaviours² and historically criminal acts and mental states have been inextricably linked. Some people thought that people commit crimes because of their mental urges as in rape cases 43% of rape victims are unknown to accused³ so if victim and accused doesn't know each other and have no enmity relation the accused commits rape in most case for satisfy their sexual desires and at the end mental urges there are many other example as people with command hallucinations disorder they also do act only just because of satisfy their mental urges⁵.

From Aristotle we got the point that "Change of state" can creates any movement so any change of mental state can creates any movement or act whether the act can be right or wrong, so in this sense the variables which may cause change of the state of mind may held liable for such act, exactly same what happen in determination of criminal liabilities of person who suffers mental defects. Any prudent person is always aware about the nature and consequences of any wrong but when a person suffers from mental disorder, this defect changes his state of mind and he cannot measure the nature of such act as a prudent person can, so criminal justice systems exempts these

¹ 'Mental Health Services in Bangladesh' (NTV) <<https://ntvbd.com/bangladesh/41500/>> accessed 23 June 2024.

² 'Mental Health and Criminal Law' (NCBI) <<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8554893/>> accessed 23 June 2024.

² 'Mental Health in Bangladesh' (NCBI Bookshelf) <<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK537064/>> accessed 23 June 2024.

³ 'Insanity and Mental Health' (PubMed) <<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/15520939/>> accessed 23 June 2024

⁵ 'Factors Increasing the Likelihood of Acting on Command Hallucinations' (SMI Adviser) <https://smiadviser.org/knowledge_post/what-factors-increase-a-person-acting-on-command-hallucinations-toharm-others> accessed 23 June 2024.

person from liability on two grounds (for not able to understand the nature of the act and for not being aware of the consequence of the act at the time of commission).

In ancient times it was believed that a person does not commit crime of his own initiative rather it is at the instigation of evil or any antigod spirit⁴ but the modern criminal justice system believes in the principle of personal responsibility. Which begs the question then why the body should be punished for the actions done due to the mental state. Since the criminal justice system is all about legalities and statutory requirements that directs punishment to the body for the crime caused.

Today although the individual's liability is established, law also allows the scope to take mental state in consideration and the culpability of an individual even after committing a crime punishable by death can differ varyingly considering the mental state/ psychological condition. As in section 84 of the Penal code argues that in absence of mental sanity if any person do any wrongful act on which he doesn't understand the nature and consequences of the act may not be liable for such act⁵. In case of Nikhil Chandra vs state the accused got acquittal for absence of culpability in his mind. So mental defects or mental element of crime is been a long issue to discuss.

In most countries of the world including Bangladesh, have a provision of acquittal on the grounds of mental unsoundness⁶ But compared to other developed countries, the acquittal process in Bangladesh feel some lacking due to procedural default⁷. While proper and specific skillful management is required during trial for detection of mental health issues, the existing legal provisions on the matter due to dearth of case law and developments poses another challenge in proving one's mental issues. Moreover, according to a research done by in Bangladesh around 70% of prisoners suffer various mental health related issues for improper management, overcrowding in the jail ,drugs but alarming issue is around 63 prisons have no doctor, it's a complete negligence and violation of fundamental rights of getting proper medical treatment of prisoners⁸.

This paper will discuss how mental health and criminal justice system works intersectionally in Bangladesh by explaining the scope of insanity, International prospective and Bangladesh prospective of infinity defense, effect of insanity in before after and during trial, challenges of clamming the defense of insanity, legal Framework, consequences of prisoners who felt mental issues in Jail and afterwards some recommendation with context of internationals.

⁴ 'The Representation of Crime and Criminals in Ancient Greece' (Academia.edu) <https://www.academia.edu/32880423/The_Representation_of_Crime_and_Criminals_in_ancient_Greece> accessed 23 June 2024.

⁵ 'Penal Code 1860: Section 84' (Bangladesh Code).

⁶ 'Code of Criminal Procedure 1898: Section 369' (Bangladesh Code).

⁷ 'Mental Health Challenges in Bangladesh and Way Forwards' (ResearchGate)

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/362485168_Mental_health_challenges_in_Bangladesh_and_way_forwards> accessed 23 June 2024.

⁸ '63 Jails Have No Doctors' (The Daily Star) <<https://www.thedailystar.net/frontpage/63-jails-have-no-doctors1405240?amp>> accessed 23 June 2024.

2. Scope of Insanity:

Mental illness is a very common phenomenon in human life⁹, according to a survey by the World Health Organization, one in eight people is mentally ill¹⁰. Trouble arises mainly when a person claims medical insanity as an excuse for a crime, but the law does not allow such an excuse rather law requires prove and evidence, this evidentiary requirement of law differentiates insanity in 3 types such as Medical insanity, Legal insanity and Criminal insanity¹¹.

Medical science interpret insanity in the different way as the law interprets it. Doctors says mental disorder, mental illness or others term but lawyers called “UN SOUNDNESS OF MIND” and law as well. Generally those who are mentally ill and under the treatment of a registered psychiatric but are capable of normal understanding are medically insane¹² and those who commit a crime and while committing it are incapable of understanding the nature of the crime and its consequences are legally insane and may get free from the liability¹³. On the other hand, those who are convicted after committing a crime and are mentally disturbed during their post-conviction prison term are criminally insane¹⁴. For a very clear idea we are discussing medical insanity, legal insanity and criminal insanity with tables and exploring differences between medical and legal insanity.

Medically Insane:

Medical insanity, often referred to as mental weakness, encompasses a range of mental health conditions that may impair an individual's cognitive or emotional functioning¹⁵. This umbrella term includes disorders such as anxiety, depression and other psychiatric conditions that may necessitate medical attention and treatment. However, being medically insane does not necessarily render an individual legally insane. The emphasis in medical insanity is on the individual's mental health and wellbeing, with the primary goal being the diagnosis, treatment and management of the mental disorder¹⁶. Individuals experiencing medical insanity may still possess the capacity to make informed decisions and lead relatively normal lives with appropriate medical intervention¹⁷.

⁹ 'Which Mental Disorder is Most Commonly Comorbid with Alcoholism?' (America's Rehab Campuses) <<https://www.americasrehabcampuses.com/addiction/mental-health/which-mental-disorder-is-most-commonlycomorbid-with-alcoholism/>> accessed 23 June 2024.

¹⁰ 'World Mental Health Day 2023' (WHO) <<https://www.who.int/campaigns/world-mental-health-day/2023>> accessed 23 June 2024.

¹¹ 'The Insanity Defense' (Open Textbook Library) <<https://open.lib.umn.edu/criminallaw/chapter/6-1-the-insanitydefense/>> accessed 23 June 2024.

¹² 'What Does It Mean to Be Clinically Insane?' (Quora) <<https://www.quora.com/What-does-it-mean-to-beclinically-insane>> accessed 23 June 2024.

¹³ 'Lunacy Act, 1912: Section 21883' (Bangladesh Code) <<http://bdlaws.minlaw.gov.bd/act-75/section-21883.html>> accessed 23 June 2024.

¹⁴ Cornell Law School, 'Criminal Insanity' (Legal Information Institute) <https://www.law.cornell.edu/wex/criminal_insanity> accessed 23 June 2024.

¹⁵ 'Insanity' (PubMed) <<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31033643/>> accessed 23 June 2024.

¹⁶ 'Insanity Defense' (Wikipedia) <<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Insanity>> accessed 23 June 2024.

¹⁷ 'Define Insane: How to Know Whether Someone is Insane or Just Different' (BetterHelp)

A common misconception is that people who are idiot or not capable of memorize things are idiot or vagabond but not medically insane. There are different types of medical insanities and the number of cases, causes and symptoms are discussed in the table below;

Name of Disorder	Experienced	Cause	Symptoms
Anxiety Disorder (58m Child)	301 millions worry.	Excessive fear and ,unsocial behaviours.	Panic attack
Depression	280 millions (23 m Child and guilt,	Feeling excessive low concentration.	Always sad, Poor adolocents swlfworth.
Bipolar Disorder	40 millions	Alternating Talkativeness,	depressive racing thought, episodes increased self stream.
Post Traumatic disorder	stress Almost victims of crime	ery Excessive threat and horrorness	Avoidance activity, ,situations. of any people
Schizophrenia	1 in 300	Depression, delusion	Hallucination, Loneliness
Eating Disorder			
Disruptive behaviour	11 millions	Family, Education	Unsocial behave
Neurodevelopmental disorder	9 millions		

SOURCE- WHO-2019

Legal insanity:

Section 84 of the Penal Code¹⁸ deals with legal insanity but this section does not provide any definition of insanity, instead of insanity the word unsoundness of mind is used, making the insanity defense more difficult¹⁹. This section provides that nothing is an offense which when done by a person is due to an unsoundness of mind or he is capable of understanding the nature of the act or he does not know whether the act is right or wrong. Basically this test of right or wrong comes from the M'Naughten rule or case where the person is not aware of right or wrong while doing the original act, if not then he can be released from liabilities²⁰.

Understanding the roots of legal insanity requires a glance back in time. The first recorded case dealing with the law of insanity dates back to 1724 in the United Kingdom with *R v. Arnold*^{21,22}. In this case, Edward Arnold attempted to kill Lord Onslow and evidence revealed that Arnold was suffering from a mental disorder. The rule introduced was called the Wild Beast test to testify good or evil behind the act. Later, the Delusion test was introduced in the Hatfield case in 1812, and the Right or Wrong test was introduced in the Bowler case in 1812 also the Durham test introduced in this age but those tests weren't correctly functioning then. The [M'Naughten Rule](#)²⁴, established in 19th-century England, remains a foundational test in many jurisdictions, assessing whether the accused knew the difference between right and wrong during the commission of the offense. This test was introduced with four principles such as firstly, criminals will be punished even if they are partially delusional. Secondly, every person is prudent and sane. Thirdly, the insanity defense must be sought before hearing and fourthly, the medical expertise will only give his opinion about the mental disorder; the insanity defense will be decided by the judges²³.

Since unsoundness of mind is established in the law of Bangladesh, the concept of unsoundness of mind is influenced by the concept of non-compos mentis, which means not of sound mind. Basically, unsoundness refers to four types of people: an idiot who knows nothing and his own name; secondly, the mad, not composed by illness; third, the lunatic, who is mad; and the drunkard, who has drunk alcohol²⁶. So these four types of people may get exempted from criminal liability if they

¹⁸ 'The Penal Code, 1860' (Bangladesh Code) <<http://bdlaws.minlaw.gov.bd/act-details-11.html>> accessed 23 June 2024.

¹⁹

²⁰ 'Insanity' (Britannica) <<https://www.britannica.com/topic/insanity>> accessed 23 June 2024.

²¹ 'Mental Health and Criminal Law' (NCBI) <<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2710106/>> accessed 23 June 2024.

²² 'Not Guilty by Reason of Insanity' (Contra Costa County) <<https://www.contracosta.ca.gov/952/Not-Guilty-byReason-of-Insanity>> accessed 23 June 2024.

²³ 'The M'Naughten Rule' (FindLaw) <<https://www.findlaw.com/criminal/criminal-procedure/the-m-naghtenrule.html>> accessed 23 June 2024.

can prove it by evidences, it's so frustrating that if a drunk person do any offence and successfully prove that he was not on his mind may free from liability that's why we can follow the American Law Institute test by replacing M Naughten test. This is discussed later in this paper.

²⁶

Differences between medical and legal insanity:

Understanding the differences between medical and legal insanity is crucial for both healthcare professionals involved in treating mental illnesses and legal professionals dealing with cases where mental health may be a factor in criminal responsibility²⁴.

Here's a table to elaborate the key differences between medical and legal insanity:

Aspect	Medical Insanity	Legal Insanity
Definition	Refers to mental illness requiring medical treatment.	Legal determination of lack of criminal responsibility.
Purpose	Focuses on health and well-being of the individual.	Pertains to legal system, assessing criminal liability.

²⁴ 'Difference Between Medical and Legal Insanity' (LawBhoomi) <<https://lawbhoomi.com/difference-betweenmedical-and-legal-insanity/>> accessed 23 June 2024.

Decision-Making Capacity	May not necessarily impact general decision-making.	Often implies a lack of decision-making capacity in legal matters.
Determining Factors	Diagnosed by healthcare professionals based on medical criteria.	Determined by legal standards, often involving assessments by mental health experts.
Consequences	Leads to medical treatment and therapy.	Can result in legal consequences, such as commitment to a psychiatric institution.
Burden of Proof	Typically diagnosed based on medical evidence.	The accused often bears the burden of proving legal insanity.

Criminal insanity

Many consider criminal insanity and legal insanity to be similar but there are some subtle differences between legal insanity and criminal insanity. Legal insanity claim is to be presented to the court during trial and the court can exonerate the defendant if it so discretionary and is proved²⁵.

Criminal insanity usually occurs when a person's mental condition deteriorates and is under treatment after a criminal conviction and imprisonment²⁶.

In USA Before the 1970's, the public outcry over a jury finding a person "not guilty by reason of insanity" ("NGRI") was not nearly as great as it is today. In that time period, insanity acquitees regularly spent many years (even a lifetime) locked in institutions for the criminally insane²⁷. An

²⁵ Cornell Law School, 'Criminal Insanity' (Legal Information Institute)

<https://www.law.cornell.edu/wex/criminal_insanity> accessed 23 June 2024.

²⁶ 'The Meaning of Criminal Insanity' (NCJRS) <<https://www.ojp.gov/ncjrs/virtual-library/abstracts/meaningcriminal-insanity>> accessed 23 June 2024.

²⁷ 'Criminal Insanity and Mental Health' (Citizens Information)

insanity acquittal was a showing of compassion and a recognition of the cruelty to inflict punishment on someone who did not know his actions were wrong²⁸.

In the past twenty years, however, a more rapid release of NGRI's from hospitals has been evident in USA . This pattern of early release is due to two factors: (1) court rulings that insanity acquitees are entitled to the same constitutional due process and equal protection rights of civil patients; this makes it more difficult to keep an individual in a hospital after recovering from mental illness; and (2) advances in psychiatric treatment. Now a days a new proposition is introduced that is “ Guilty but mentally insane” these people may get treatment in jail hospital as per Mental disorder act 2006 of USA²⁹.

In Bangladesh, sometimes this proposition recognized as OYSHEE³⁰ case where she murder her father and mother when she was intoxicated by drugs our apex court punish her by life imprisonment and give some extent of less punishment for the ground of unsoundness of mind and she also getting treatment I the jail. But in many cases after conviction the person who felt mental disorder negligently avoided but it should not they are also human and have some rights of treatment.

²⁸ <<https://www.citizensinformation.ie/en/justice/criminal-law/criminal-trial/criminal-insanity-and-mental-health/>> accessed 23 June 2024.

²⁹ 'Criminal Insanity: Cases, Law, and Defense' (Study.com) <<https://study.com/academy/lesson/criminal-insanitycases-law-defense.html>> accessed 23 June 2024.

³⁰ 'From Murder to Religion: How Is Oishee Spending Her Time?' (Dhaka Tribune) <<https://www.dhakatribune.com/amp/bangladesh/246803/from-murder-to-religion-how-is-oishee-spending>> accessed 23 June 2024.

3. Insanity as a defense in criminal trial in Bangladesh

Just suffering from a mental disorder is not sufficient to prove insanity as defense. Insanity defense is a legal concept, not a clinical or medical one³⁴. This is contrasted with an excuse of provocation, in which the defendant is responsible, but the responsibility is lessened due to a temporary mental state³⁵. So as court accept the insanity defense doesn't mean fully free from all kind of responsibility. Law believes on the principle that "No offender should be unredressed"

The history of insanity defense in criminal trial dates back to ancient times with mentions found in the Code of Hammurabi and Roman law³⁶. However one must attest that the determination of criminal liability in true sense has always been a challenge specifically if the criminal suffers from mental disorder or psychiatric conditions because suffering from a mental disorder or temporary insanity does not necessarily bar a person from leading a normal life later on, e.g "IRAQI INFANTICIDE MOTHER" case, an Iraqi mother killed her 1 year old son by pressing pillow, police arrested her and she claims insanity defense but court after examination rejected her claim and after conviction she founds at her abnormal behavior, she was suffering from post- pregnancy stressed disorder or postpartum depression, mental disorder which arises after giving birth of any child for tiredness, worry and guiltiness³⁷. So in this case what was the mechanism to determine the liability of such women, to understand this we need to know about medico-legal science³⁸.

Insanity is a defense that allows the accused to defend or get acquittal or reduced punishment for a person on ground that the concerned offender was suffering from some kind of mental disorder or condition or was not mentally capable to form the required criminal intention to commit such wrongful act. Men s rea refers to the intention or guilty mind and mental element for committing a wrongful act. The requirement of proving men s rea or guilty mind is not a new idea, one of the oldest law code of Ur-Nammu and Hamburabi also advocated on this. The code of Hamburabi in absence of men s rea or mental presence advocated for reduced capital punishment and states that if any person is killed on occasion of sudden quarrel and accused able to promise to god that the murder wasn't willful then the accused shall not punished by death, if any person injures by such act accused shall liable to bear the medical expenses.

'Mental Health and Criminal Law' (NCBI) <<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4676201/bin/IJPsyM37-381g001.jpg><https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4676201/>> accessed 23 June 2024

³⁵ 'Insanity Defense' (Wikipedia) <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Insanity_defense> accessed 23 June 2024.

³⁶ 'Code of Hammurabi and the Insanity Defense' (Reddit)

<https://www.reddit.com/r/AskHistorians/comments/8ebd9y/code_of_hammurabi_and_the_insanity_defense/?rdt=59714> accessed 23 June 2024.

³⁷ 'Postpartum Depression' (March of Dimes)

<<https://www.marchofdimes.org/findsupport/topics/postpartum/postpartumdepression#:~:text=It's%20strong%20feelings%20of%20sadness,needs%20treatment%20to%20get%20better>> accessed 23 June 2024.

³⁸ SpringerLink, 'Forensic Psychiatry and Psychology' (Springer) <<https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-3030-47852-0>> accessed 23 June 2024.

Insanity defense is a concern of medico-legal science which refers to the interaction between medical science and law³⁹. Law can declare any person insane not on its own spheres but on the basis of scientific explanation of medical science so these two sciences interact together in the determination of legal insanity. Generally in any criminal trial, the burden of proof lies on the prosecution or complainant, so the offenders are considered as innocent until proven guilty in the preliminary stage of any trial and the prosecution have proved the actus reus and mens rea for getting sentence against the offender. This is the general rule, but exceptional situation arises when any defense lawyer or offender claims before court that the offender is mentally incapable or insane or have any psychiatric disease and at the time of committing the offence was not capable to understand that what he is doing is wrong or the consequences of the act and under penal laws insanity defense is claimed and the burden of prove shifts on the accused. As insanity is a psychological and neurological condition, the court has to rely on medical science and expert opinion to decide. Insanity defense stands on two points, whether the accused is competent to stand before court and whether the accused was capable of understand the nature of crime at the time of the act.

Courts mostly follow M’Naghten rule, Irresistible persistent rule, Durham rule and other principles to determine insanity in a trial to ensure proper determination of insanity American supreme court has tried to find pathway about this matter by categorizing “Mental state” in two parts and has developed an idea called “Mental Automatism” where mental state has been divided as-

- **Insane automatism:** This refers to insanity derived from factors which are beyond the control of a human. For instance, in **R v Hennessy [1989] 1 WLR 297** the defendant, an insulin dependent diabetic did not take any insulin and went without food for a period of days which caused him to suffer from hyperglycaemia. In this case the Court held that the defendant’s behaviour was caused by the internal factor of the non-regulation of the blood sugar and as such the correct defense of his behavior was insane automatism⁴⁰, this sustains as an insanity defense and it may extend even to complete defense.
- **Non insane automatism:** This concept is inspired by the irresistible persistence principle and refers to insanity that can be controlled as it involves external factors. In the case **R v Quick [1973] QB 910** The defendant was charged with assault. He had taken insulin and then consumed some food and drink which caused him to suffer from hyperglycaemia. It was held by the Court that the external factor of the insulin caused the behaviour and thus the correct defense was non-insane automatism⁴¹ So if the act of

³⁹ 'Medico-Legal Aspects of Insanity' (Uttar Pradesh Police)

<https://uppolice.gov.in/writereaddata/uploadedcontent/Web_Page/18_11_2013_16_56_7_Medico_legal_ppt.pdf> accessed 23 June 2024.

'The Insanity Defense: What You Should Know' (Crim-Law) <<https://www.crim-law.info/the-insanity-defense-what-you-should-know.html>> accessed 23 June 2024.

LawTeacher, 'Insanity Automatism Intoxication' (LawTeacher)

<<https://www.lawteacher.net/lectures/criminallaw/denials-defences/insanity-automatism-intoxication/>> accessed 23 June 2024.

insanity derives from external factors of claimant then it can't be sustained or if sustained it may lead to partial or may get reduced of sentence.

On the basis of this principle we can categorized the insanity defense as three. Those are

- **Complete defenses:** This defense ensures complete release of the offender from criminal liability. The accused have to prove his non awareness about the occurrence and its consequences. In case of R vs Henessy, R vs Laura fair, Constance Fisher and many other cases, accused were completely acquitted from their criminal liabilities and got proper treatment for their mental illness. Mainly persons who are incompetent to stand before court get acquittal. Many legal authors are in opposition of this defense as they believe that the offender is acquitted only on ground of mental condition which is a miscarriage of justice from the perspective of victim. On the other hand jurists from the human rights concerned perspective support this proposition because they believe that punishing a person with mental illness unaware of what he is doing and it's consequences is a complete violation of human rights.
- **Partial defenses:** As we know insanity plea is an affirmatory defense, to claiming insanity defense the accused have to admit their offence and then plea insanity defense for reduced sentence. Most of the time accused didn't get complete defense or acquittal on plea of insanity³¹. Mostly muslim countries where application of this defense is so complex³². Person who are found guilty but mentally ill are capable of getting partial defense. This defense may reduce sentence on affirmation and plead insanity. Usually partial defenses are determined by application of Irresistible persistence rule. Generally we can see that partial defense shall claim on pre-trial or trial stage but sometimes it claimed after conviction and got reduced of sentence as in case of Oishee Rahman vs State³³³⁴ she had killed her father and mother when she was drunk the court sentences her death and after this judgement the defense lawyer claim insanity defense and on the ground of insanity Oyshee got free from death and sentenced for life imprisonment⁴⁵.
- **Excusatory defenses:** This defense mainly focuses on the mental absence at the time of committing the wrongful act claiming was done on provocation of the victim. Accused claims justification of their act as in self-defense. Recently in Bangladesh a

³¹ Cornell Law School, 'Partial Defense' (Legal Information Institute)

<https://www.law.cornell.edu/wex/partial_defense> accessed 23 June 2024.

³² SpringerLink, 'Forensic Psychiatry and Psychology' (Springer) <<https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-3030-47852-0>> accessed 23 June 2024.

³³ 'Oishee Given Death Penalty' (The Daily Star) <<https://www.thedailystar.net/frontpage/oishee-given-deathpenalty-171697?amp>> accessed 23 June 2024.

³⁴ SCOB 18

women killed her husband³⁵ in a flat and escaped to Canada and leaving a note that states that the victim has threatened her several times and made her life hell. Application of this defense is so narrow because if the court start to entertain this kind of defense it will tends citizen to avoid law and encourage to taking revenge against wrong. Justificatory defense as which says about absence of mental culpability is an extended version of this kind of defense.

There are many challenge on plea of insanity those are discussed in the next chapter.

Bangladesh on insanity defense:

According to World Health Organization (WHO) almost 65% people of Bangladesh suffers from various types of mental disorder such as anxiety, depression, schizophrenia, hallucination and others. These are kind of medical insanity but legal insanity is broader than these. Legal and criminal insanity are concerns of law ,law don't entertains mere medical insanity to consider insanity as defense because law only see absence or presence of mind in the particular moment when the wrongful act was done, so if a person has a history of mental disorder or SAD Seasonal affecting disorder and at the time of commission the offence he was not insane but in the time of trial he became insane in this situation the accused cannot claim any defense so if in Bangladesh we say that insanity defense is used to protect the actual insane person it might be wrong rather it is to protect the accused who was insane at the moment of commission such offence.

On plea of insanity : Bangladesh regulates insanity defense with section 84 of Penal code, the offender or their lawyer have to plea insanity in the trial stage but Bangladeshi lawyer and people are not mostly aware about this defense as in case of OYSHEE plea of insanity was plead at the appeal stage and court accepts the plea, so who knows if the plea of insanity plead at the lower court the verdict may be different in this case, In another case RIFAT SHARIF KILLINGG Minni was wife of Rifat and a conspirator of Rifat murder in this case the plea of insanity regarding Minni was plead in appeal stage so Bangladeshi lawyer mostly not aware about this defense and there is no appropriate data about this matter.

On burden of proof : After claiming the defense the court declare to doctor for examination of the accused and after examines the accused the doctor submits the report to the court and court if there is prima facie proof of insanity then the court permits the accused or defense lawyer to appears before court with evidence of insanity. So the burden of proving insanity lies on the accused in Bangladesh. Evidence act 1872 section 105 states that if any person claims any specific matter burden of proving the claim lies on the person who claims such.

Procedure: As we mentioned before that law consider as insane two types of person- person who is incompetent to understand the trial procedure and person who was unaware about the act doing is wrong. The code of criminal procedure section 464 discuss about power of court to adjourn the

³⁵ 'Woman Comes from Canada to Bangladesh, Kills Man and Then Flies Back' (The Financial Express) <<https://thefinancialexpress.com.bd/national/woman-comes-from-canada-to-bangladesh-kills-man-and-then-fliesback>> accessed 23 June 2024.

trial and ensure medical treatment or relative custody or release the accused on bail bond of any close relative that the accused never harm to another for not any specified time on ground of nonunderstanding the trial procedure and unable to produce evidence before court in most cases it was rejected by the court because the presumption of the court regarding this matter is against the accused.

Custody: In Bangladesh if the accused is unable to understand the court proceeding he may transfer in the rehabilitation center or may give to the close relatives custody according to section 471 of the code of criminal procedure. But this custody only to grant on the matter where the accused is unable to understand the trial procedure during mental disorder or insanity so in matter of person who claims that at the time of commits the crime he was completely unaware about the wrongful act this kind of custody might not be granted by court.

Acquittal; The accused who is unable to understand the trial procedure if the court satisfied that there is no possibilities to being well or being capable then the court can acquit the accused on this ground according to section 470 of the code of criminal procedure. But applicability of this section is so narrow. So if any person got acquittal on this ground he may deliver to family of the accused according to section 475 of the CRPC if the accused has no family he may transfer to the support center.

Medical treatment: In Bangladesh the medical treatment of any accused are regulated by the Mental health act 2018, if any person in trial suffering any mental disorder he shall get proper treatment but in reality there is a huge gap in law to application, research says approximately 75% of prisoners are suffering from mental disorder and not getting proper treatment and medical facilities in prison are very poor. We interviewed 8 convicted persons who were in jail and after getting free they all can never back to their normal life because the environment of the prisons in Bangladesh also so poor. So In Bangladesh there are no post prison treatment system it's an injustice to the offender because after getting punishment the offender as a human being deserves a normal life. Lack of proper care of prisoners is also an alarming issue in Bangladesh because person after convicted if feels any mental disability they consult with the medical officer of the jail but medical officer of any jail is not a specialist of psychiatric. Government requires every jail medical center shall appoint at least one psychologist but it no followed almost everywhere. To ensure proper mental treatment in Bangladeshi prison is very alarming issues because the environment of prison is very poor as there lives 84 thousands plus prisoners where the capacity is only of 41 thousands, there are other issues as like drug related issues, according to a doctor of prison almost 80% prisoners with mental disorder are suffering from frug related mental disorder.

As like other countries like UK, USA , Australia Bangladesh has a huge gap on the concerning issues relating to mental disorder.

Country	Time	Forum	Plead by	Burden of prove	Principle & Law followed	Consequence
United Kingdom	Pre-trial and post trial stage or at any stage of the case	Concerned court where the case is trialable	Lawyer of the accused	Prosecution	M. Naughten rule, Irresistible impulse rule, Durham rule and Mental health act 1959 and Trial of lunatics act 1883	The accused get complete defence and get proper treatment. Sometimes accused get medical facilities after imprisonment
United States of America	At any stage of the case	Concerned court or tribunal	Lawyer of the accused at pre trial stage and by the jailer if found on imprisonment	Defence Lawyer with medical certificate	Along with M. Naughten rule, Guidelines of American Law institute, Federal criminal lawyers rule, Federal rule of evidence, Insanity defence Reform act 1984.	Permits complete, partial and executory defence in some context and give proper medical facilities, permits post trial plea and ensure after imprisonment treatment.

Australia	Pre Trial stage	Court for mental impairment	Accused or their lawyer.	Accused	Commonwealth criminal code, M Naughten rule	Mostly partial defence and grant complete defence if prove beyond any reasonable doubt. No post trial treatment system.
India	Pre trial stage	Where the offence is trialable	Accused or Lawyer	Accused	Indian penal code section 84 and M.Naughten rule.	Partial defence and medical treatment after being well may be trialable.
Bangladesh	Pre trial stage	Concerned court	Accused Or Lawyer	Accused	Section 84 Penal code 1860, Evidence act 105 and Mental health act 2018, Code of criminal procedure 1898 section 360-372	Partial defence.

4. Legal framework regarding mental health in Bangladesh.

Mental health is an ignored subject matter in Bangladesh³⁶. Lawyers, judges and almost all accused are not aware about mental health related issue, in many case defense lawyer didn't even claim insanity defense where the accused was suffered serious mental illness. Mentally ill peoples are also human being they also have constitutionally protected rights as they are also citizen of the country. Bangladesh as like other countries have laws relating to mental health and protection of

³⁶ 'The MHA 2018: A Special Legislative Framework for Mental Health' (NCBI)

<<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8554921/#:~:text=The%20MHA%202018%2C%20a%20special,judicial%20examination%20of%20mental%20health>> accessed 23 June 2024.

insane human rights³⁷. In legal arena protection, treatment and rights of an insane can be divided into four time frames those are

- Rights of person claimed insanity before trial
- Treatment of insane during trial
- Protection of people with mental disorder after trial or in jail.
- Post imprisonment protection of people with mental defect (Not applicable in Bangladesh)³⁸

Laws relating to Rights of Persons Claiming Insanity Defense Before Trial in Bangladesh

The insanity defense is a legal doctrine that allows people with severe mental disorders to avoid criminal liability if they are incapable of understanding the nature or wrongfulness of their actions. In Bangladesh, the rights of persons claiming the insanity defense before trial are governed by a combination of constitutional provisions, statutory law and judicial practice³⁹. We examine the legal framework, procedures and challenges related to the rights of persons claiming the insanity defense before trial in Bangladesh and provide recommendations for improving the system⁴⁰.

Constitution of Bangladesh

The Constitution of Bangladesh guarantees fundamental rights to all citizens, including the right to life, personal liberty, and protection from discrimination (Articles 27, 31, and 32)⁴¹. We cannot deny that the people with mental defect are valid citizen of our country so these provisions apply to persons with mental disorders, ensuring their fundamental human rights. Article 27 of the constitution states that every citizen of the country shall get equal protection of law, so as to get insanity defense and to get proper examination and treatment by mental health is a legal obligation of the government to ensure⁴².

Penal Code, 1860

Section 84 of the Penal Code, 1860⁴³, provides exemption from criminal liability for acts committed by persons of unsound mind. The term “Unsoundness of mind” is defined in second chapter of this paper. This section states that an act is not an offense if the person doing it is

³⁷ 'Reshaping Mental Health Legislation in Bangladesh' (The Daily Star) <<https://www.thedailystar.net/law-ourrights/news/reshaping-mental-health-legislation-bangladesh-3419261>> accessed 23 June 2024.

³⁸ 'Legal Framework for Mental Health in Bangladesh Inadequate' (The Daily Star) <<https://www.thedailystar.net/city/news/legal-framework-mental-health-inadequate-198233720of>> accessed 23 June 2024.

³⁹ 'Global Mental Health: A Call for Increased Action' (The Lancet Psychiatry) <[https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lanpsy/article/PIIS2215-0366\(19\)30028-8/fulltext](https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lanpsy/article/PIIS2215-0366(19)30028-8/fulltext)> accessed 23 June 2024.

⁴⁰ 'PubMed' (National Library of Medicine) <<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>> accessed 23 June 2024.

⁴¹ 'Insanity Act 1912' (Bangladesh Code) <<http://bdlaws.minlaw.gov.bd/act-367.html>> accessed 23 June 2024.

⁴² Ibid

⁴³ 'The Penal Code, 1860' (Bangladesh Code) <<http://bdlaws.minlaw.gov.bd/act-11.html>> accessed 23 June 2024.

incapable of knowing the nature of the act or that it is wrongful or contrary to law because of infirmity of mind⁴⁴.

The Code of Criminal Procedure, 1898 (CrPC)

Sections 364 to 375 of the CrPC⁴⁵ outline procedures for dealing with accused persons who are deemed to be an insane. Section 364 defines the procedures for inquiring into the unsoundness of mind of an accused person. So the accused can claim insanity in preliminary stage of the case. After his claim the court seeks opinion of civil surgeon and after testified by the surgeon the court may postpone or adjourned the investigation and trial as section 365 states But if there is no reasonable ground to believe before court that the accused can be insane court can reject such claim as per 17DLR68⁵⁷. So the insanity must be proved beyond any reasonable doubt and by the opinion of the civil surgeon and other medical expertise {5LNJ2016(2)22}⁵⁸.

Court after satisfied that the accused is not able to stand before court may order to release the accused or to take custody of the insane person but the custody should not in the jail rather it should be a place where the insane can get better environment to recover, the custody also can be in the family or close friend of the accused if court satisfied on that the accused shall get proper care and⁴⁷do no danger to others and appear before court at any time 7BLD432⁵⁹.

In Bangladesh without some exceptions to get released from the criminal proceeding by getting insanity defense does not mean to get fully free from all liability, So after being capable of understand the trial and defend himself person who get insanity defense may try again for their committed offence if the accused is get the insanity defense on ground of non-understanding of the trial. On the other hand if the accused get the insanity defense on ground of insanity during the commission of the crime or non-understanding of the nature and consequences of the wrongful act what they have done in this ground the accused may get acquittal Enayet Hossain Vs state⁶⁰.

Rights of Persons Claimed Insanity Defense

- **Humane Treatment:** Persons claiming the insanity defense have the right to humane and dignified treatment as mandated by the Mental Health Act, 2018. This includes appropriate medical care, respect for their privacy and protection from abuse or neglect⁴⁸.
- **Right to Information:** Accused and their family members have the right to be informed about the nature of the mental health evaluation, the legal process involved and the implications of the insanity defense.

⁴⁴ Ibid

⁴⁵ 'The Lunacy Act, 1912' (Bangladesh Code) <<http://bdlaws.minlaw.gov.bd/act-75.html>> accessed 23 June 2024.

⁴⁶ DLR68⁵⁸

{5LNJ2016(2)22}.

⁴⁷ BLD432.⁶⁰

7BLC577-

⁴⁸ 'Bangladesh Laws' (Ministry of Law, Justice and Parliamentary Affairs) <<http://bdlaws.minlaw.gov.bd/act1273.html>> accessed 23 June 2024.

- **Right to Legal Representation:** Legal representatives play a crucial role in advocating for the rights of the accused, ensuring that their mental health needs are addressed, and safeguarding their interests throughout the legal process.

□ Right to Medical Care □ Right to a Speedy Trial

In conclusion the rights of persons claiming the insanity defense before trial in Bangladesh are protected by a combination of constitutional provisions, statutory law and judicial practice. However, significant challenges remain in terms of stigma, awareness, resources and implementation. Addressing this challenge requires a multi-pronged approach involving legal reform, increased resources, improved training and efforts to reduce stigma. By taking these steps, Bangladesh can ensure that individuals claiming the insanity defense receive the care and justice they deserve, uphold their rights, and promote their well-being within the criminal justice system⁴⁹.

Protection of people with mental disorder:

Historically, the legal framework for mental health regulation in Bangladesh was rooted in colonial-era legislation. The Lunacy Act of 1912, inherited from British India, was the primary law regulating the treatment and institutionalization of persons with mental disorders. The Act was mainly custodial and did not emphasize the rights of individuals or provide for their rehabilitation. The Mental Health Act, 2018 replaced the old Lunacy Act of 1912⁵⁰ and introduced comprehensive provisions for the treatment and protection of persons with mental disorders. It emphasizes the right of persons involved in the criminal justice system to receive humane and dignified treatment⁵¹.

The MHA 2018 focuses on the following key areas:

- **Protection of rights:** It guarantees the rights of people with mental disorders, ensuring that they receive humane and dignified treatment. It emphasizes the need for informed consent, privacy and the right to access mental health services.
- **Institutional Framework:** The Act establishes a Mental Health Review Board to oversee the implementation of mental health policies and address complaints. It also mandates the creation of mental health facilities and community-based services.

⁴⁹ Directorate General of Health Services, 'Notice' (DGHS)

<https://dghs.portal.gov.bd/sites/default/files/files/dghs.portal.gov.bd/notices/e27171cb_a80b_42d4_99ad_40095adf31b/2022-08-16-08-42-> accessed 23 June 2024.

https://dghs.portal.gov.bd/sites/default/files/files/dghs.portal.gov.bd/notices/e27171cb_a80b_42d4_99ad_40095adf31b/2022-08-16-08-42-

⁵⁰ 'Newly Enacted Mental Health Law in Bangladesh' (Cambridge)

<https://www.cambridge.org/core/services/aopcambridgecore/content/view/0E0DE9EADE123D5AE043225FDB4AD92D/S2056474021000015a.pdf/newly_enacted_mental_health_law_in_bangladesh.pdf> accessed 23 June 2024.

⁵¹ 'New Mental Health Act in Bangladesh: Unfinished Agenda' (ResearchGate)

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/329813584_New_Mental_Health_Act_in_Bangladesh_unfinished_agenda/asaf8622e2c4936593dd45601b84f4920f.pdf/34748619/> accessed 23 June 2024.

- **Criminalization:** The law criminalized suicide, recognizing it as a mental health problem rather than a criminal act. This is a significant shift towards a more compassionate approach to mental health.

The Mental Health Act 2018 represents a significant advance in the legal protection of persons with mental illness in Bangladesh. However, effective implementation needs to address several challenges, including stigma, resource limitations, and lack of awareness. To enhance the protection and care of people with mental illness, sustained efforts and multi-sectoral collaboration are essential to ensure that these legal provisions translate into tangible benefits for those with mental health problems⁵²⁵³.

Rights of Prisoners with Mental Disorders in Bangladesh

“63 jails have no doctors”⁶⁶ it’s a headline of the daily star a prominent daily of Bangladesh, surprising fact is there are 68 jails in Bangladesh that means only 5 jails maintains the legal requirement to appoint a medical officer in jail for treatment of the prisoners. Prisoners with mental disorders represent a highly vulnerable population within the criminal justice system. In Bangladesh, legal and institutional frameworks to address the needs and rights of these individuals have historically been inadequate. In this country there are 84000 of prisoners where the capacity is for only 40000⁵⁴.

According to research study almost 75% of prisoners in Bangladesh suffers from various kinds of mental disorder and other drug related diseases, but having only 4-5 doctors for around 90000 peoples is adequate?

Interesting fact is sometimes the supreme court of Bangladesh have to intervention for ensuring medical treatment to prisoners⁵⁵. We examines some prisoners after their released they share their experiences and said **“we don’t know what is human rights in the prison, they (authority) never looks after us before we are at the stage of dying”** so from this statement it is clear that **the rights of mental disorder people in jail is not proper in Bangladesh, but as a signatory state of Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) Bangladesh has the obligation to ensure these rights of prisoners.**

⁵² 'Mental Health Services' (World Vision International) <https://www.wvi.org/sites/default/files/202206/Mental_Health_Services.pdf> accessed 23 June 2024.

⁵³ '9 Prison Doctors for 90,000 Inmates in Bangladesh' (The Daily Star) <<https://www.thedailystar.net/frontpage/9prison-doctors-for-90000-inmates-in-bangladesh-1801108?amp>> accessed 23 June 2024.

⁵⁴ 'Prison System in Bangladesh' (Scribd) <<https://www.scribd.com/document/264538959/Prison-System-in-Bangladesh>> accessed 23 June 2024.

⁵⁵ 'Save the Poor by Appointing Prison' (Dhaka Tribune) <<https://www.dhakatribune.com/amp/bangladesh/court/312926/high-court-save-the-poor-by-appointing-prison>> accessed 23 June 2024.

In conclusion, we can say that besides other issues the conditions of people with mental disorder in jail is very alarming in Bangladesh, government should increase budget⁵⁶ in this matter and also in health sector, prisoners are also human being they have the right to getting proper treatment, to show a neglected attitude to them is not legal.

5. Challenges of claiming insanity defense:

As insanity defense is a complex idea and hard to determine person's insanity⁵⁷, defense on ground of mental defect is always being a challenge⁵⁸. Schabusiness' trial for the "House of Horrors Murder" unfolds with a structured approach that separates guilt from considerations of mental health and legal insanity. The defense's strategic decisions, including refraining from immediately invoking an insanity defense, indicate a calculated approach to navigating legal complexities and ensuring a fair trial⁵⁹. We will discuss the details behind the House of Horrors Murder case and explore the challenges of an insanity defense. Later we will refer some Bangladeshi case such as Oyshee who killed her father and mother on provocation of intoxication.

Short fact and issues relating to "House of horror murder case:

On February 23, 2022, a mother in Green Bay, Wisconsin made a gruesome discovery when she found her son's severed head sitting in a bucket in her basement. Taylor Schabusiness was later charged with killing the young man, sexually abusing his body and then dismembering his body. After her arrest, Schabusiness pleaded "not guilty by reason of insanity"⁶⁰.

After being arrested by police Schabusiness informed that both she and the victim had smoked methamphetamines before engaging in consensual sex that involved the use of chains. According to Schabusiness, hers and the victim had a history of engaging in erotic asphyxiation⁶¹ during sex. So on this time the victim faced breathing problem and died, after his death Schabusiness didn't

⁵⁶ 'Prison System in Bangladesh' (LinkedIn) <<https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/prison-system-bangladesh-bdlexmanupatra>> accessed 23 June 2024.

⁵⁷ 'The Challenges of Pleading Not Guilty by Reason of Insanity' (Pumphrey Law Firm) <<https://www.pumphreylawfirm.com/blog/the-challenges-of-pleading-not-guilty-by-reason-of-insanity/>> accessed 23 June 2024.

⁵⁸ Mehrab Hasan, 'An Evaluation of Insanity Defense' (SCLS Law Review) <<https://sclsbd.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/4.-SCLS-Law-Rev-43-Mehrab-Hasan-An-Evaluation-of-Insanity-Defense.pdf>> accessed 23 June 2024.

⁵⁹ 'Insanity Defense: Past, Present, and Future' (ResearchGate) <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/283550855_Insanity_Defense_Past_Present_and_Future> accessed 23 June 2024.

⁶⁰ 'Green Bay Killing: Taylor Schabusiness' (AP News) <<https://apnews.com/article/green-bay-killing-taylor-schabusiness-9f0e1ea990f9557d72a415fd781a1e96>> accessed 23 June 2024.

⁶¹ 'Erotic Asphyxiation: What Is It?' (Healthline) <<https://www.healthline.com/health/healthy-sex/eroticasphyxiation#What-is-it>> accessed 23 June 2024.

stop to choking her neck and performed orally and also by using toys. After these she cut his male organ and other body parts by a sharp blade⁶².

In this case during opening statements, Schabusiness' defense attorney asked the jury to refrain from "jumping to conclusions" and to "keep an open mind" throughout the trial. Surprisingly, the defense did not mention their intention to pursue an insanity defense. Because the trial is divided into two phases.

- The jury will assess whether Scabbusiness is guilty of the charges against him, because the cause of death of the victim was consensual unnatural lust.
- If the jury found her guilty of any of the charges, they would consider whether she could be declared insane.

As we know insanity defense may claim on two ground

- The accused is not competent stand before court or defend himself
- The accused was no capable to understand the nature and consequences of the wrongful act which he is commission

So first question arises in any trial that whether the offender is competent to stand in trial or defend them, in this question after completing requiring steps of the proceedings psychologist Dr Lytthon certified that that Schabusiness had "Command hallucination". This is a mental condition where victim feels that someone is commanding him to do such act⁶³. Jury decided to continue trial and aims to examine the evidences on behalf. So it is the jury to finally decide on matter of competency to stand before court.

But on determination of insanity or absence mind when commission offence is difficult to prove because it should prove by clear and convincing way R and to proving this there are many factors interplays.

In light of this restrictive criteria, here are some factors contributing to the challenges of proving the insanity defense:

High standard of burden of proof:

The insanity defense serves as a critical legal mechanism that allows people accused of crimes to argue that they should not be held criminally responsible because of their state of mind at the time of the crime⁶⁴. However, asserting the insanity defense comes with significant challenges, particularly regarding the burden of proof.

⁶² . 'Murder of Shad Thyron' (Wikipedia) <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Murder_of_Shad_Thyron> accessed 23 June 2024.

⁶³ 'CommandHallucinations:AReview'(PubMed)<<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/9785279/#:~:text=Command%20hallucinations%20are%20auditory%20hallucinations,from%20innocuous%20to%20life%2Dthreatening>> accessed 23 June 2024.

⁶⁴ 'Turpin Case' (Wikipedia) <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Turpin_case> accessed 23 June 2024.

When using an insanity defense, the burden of proof shifts to the defendant, requiring them to prove their insanity by a high standard of proof⁶⁵, and the defendant must prove their insanity by "clear and convincing evidence."⁶⁶ But proving insanity to this standard can be extremely challenging due to the subjectivity of mental states and the complexity of psychiatric diagnoses.

Stigma and social taboo surrounding mental illness:

Claiming the insanity defense can carry significant social stigma. Defendants may fear for being labeled as "crazy" or dangerous, which may affect their treatment within the legal system and society⁶⁷. This stigma can prevent individuals from asserting the insanity defense, even when it may be warranted. Undoubtedly a social stigma can change decision of the court and its conceptions regarding the accused. For example, jurors may have preconceptions about mental illness, making it difficult for them to objectively view the defendant's actions from a clinical perspective.

Social taboo regarding insanity especially in rural areas of Bangladesh plays a vital role to restraining insane to take proper treatment because in rural areas people thinks that being a insane is curse of god to the whole family so the whole family of the insane have to be humiliated for the insane. A report says in Bangladesh approximately 26% of people are suffers from various types of mental disorder⁶⁸ but this is avoiding issue to the government as their 1% of whole budget are in medical sector and only 6% of that budget is for mental health and there also lack of expertise⁶⁹.

Subjectivity of mental states:

Mental health evaluations play an important role in insanity defenses, yet they are fraught with complications. Evaluating a defendant's mental state at the time of a crime requires specialized training and expertise in forensic psychology and psychiatry. Evaluators must navigate issues such as poor behavior, the effects of substance abuse, and the possibility of transient mental states during criminal behavior⁷⁰.

Determination of the mental state of the defendant at the time of the crime, often leading to a "battle of the experts"⁷¹. Typically, the defense calls experts to testify about the defendant's mental state,

⁶⁵ Cornell Law School, 'Insanity Defense' (Legal Information Institute)

<https://www.law.cornell.edu/wex/insanity_defense> accessed 23 June 2024.

⁶⁶ Cornell Law School, 'Beyond a Reasonable Doubt' (Legal Information Institute)

<https://www.law.cornell.edu/wex/beyond_a_reasonable_doubt> accessed 23 June 2024.

⁶⁷ 'Mental Illness Stigma' (Health Direct) <<https://www.healthdirect.gov.au/amp/article/mental-illness-stigma>> accessed 23 June 2024.

⁶⁸ Michael L. Perlin, 'On Sanism' (Modern Languages Research)

<<https://modernlanguagesresearch.blogs.sas.ac.uk/2020/06/17/mental-health-discourse-taboo-or-stigma/>> accessed 23 June 2024.

⁶⁹ 'Mental Health Challenges in Bangladesh and Way Forwards' (ResearchGate)

<<https://ruor.uottawa.ca/items/9b9fb35a-c3ca-45c2-814f-8df9d948a571>> accessed 23 June 2024.

⁷⁰ 'Stigma and Mental Health' (JSTOR) <<https://www.jstor.org/stable/2214189>> accessed 23 June 2024.

⁷¹ 'Subjectivity and Intersubjectivity in Psychiatric Diagnosis' (ResearchGate)

while the state presents its own experts to challenge or counter the defense experts' testimony. Diagnosing mental illness is not as clear-cut as diagnosing physical illness, and as a result, experts may have different opinions about the defendant's state of mind at the time of the crime⁷². This disparity in expert opinion adds to the complexity of insanity defense cases.

Clinical and Forensic Differences

A fundamental complication of mental health evaluations for the insanity defense lies in distinguishing between clinical psychiatric diagnoses and forensic evaluations⁷³. While clinical diagnosis focuses on understanding and treating mental disorders, forensic evaluations must assess whether a defendant's mental state meets the legal criteria for insanity. This distinction requires mental health professionals to apply specialized knowledge and skills in forensic psychology and psychiatry, often involving different methods and considerations than those used in clinical settings⁷⁴. Forensic evaluators must carefully consider the legal standards applicable in their jurisdiction, such as cognitive impairment affecting capacity or volitional impairment affecting behavioral control⁷⁵. This requires a comprehensive understanding of the legal definition of insanity and the ability to apply mental knowledge within a legal framework⁸⁹.

Temporal and retrospective assessment

Assessing a defendant's mental state at the time of the crime poses another significant challenge to the insanity defense⁷⁶. Mental health evaluations often occur months or even years after the alleged crime, requiring a retrospective evaluation of the defendant's mental state at the time of the incident. This temporal lag can complicate the accuracy and reliability of assessments, as memories may fade and the circumstances surrounding the crime may become less clear over time⁷⁷. Furthermore, factors such as substance abuse at the time of the crime, trauma, or acute stress

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/44643758_Subjectivity_and_Intersubjectivity_in_Psychiatric_Diagnosis> accessed 23 June 2024.

⁷² 'Mental State Examination (MSE)' (RCEM Learning)

<<https://www.rcemlearning.org/modules/psychiatricemergencies-for-the-adult-patient/lessons/mental-state-examination-mse/>> accessed 23 June 2024.

⁷³ 'Insanity and Competency to Stand Trial' (Forensic Psychology)

<<https://www.forensicpsychologyedu.org/insanity-and-competency-to-stand-trial/>> accessed 23 June 2024.

⁷⁴ 'Insanity and Competency' (Criminal Justice) <[https://criminal-](https://criminal-justice.iresearchnet.com/forensicpsychology/clinical-forensic-psychology/insanity-and-competency/)

[justice.iresearchnet.com/forensicpsychology/clinical-forensic-psychology/insanity-and-competency/](https://criminal-justice.iresearchnet.com/forensicpsychology/clinical-forensic-psychology/insanity-and-competency/)> accessed 23 June 2024.

⁷⁵ 'Insanity Defense' (Guide to Psychology) <<https://www.guidetopsychology.com/legal.htm>> accessed 23 June 2024. ⁸⁹ : Mark S. Komrad, 'Psychiatric Treatment of the Mentally Ill in Prisons and Jails' (PubMed)

<<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/3203269/>> accessed 23 June 2024.

⁷⁶ 'Conducting Insanity Evaluations' (ResearchGate)

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/232544246_Conducting_Insanity_Evaluations> accessed 23 June 2024.

⁷⁷ 'The Insanity Defense: Legal Standards and Clinical Assessment' (ResearchGate)

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/223399142_The_insanity_defense_Legal_standards_and_clinical_assessment> accessed 23 June 2024.

response may further complicate retrospective assessment. Mental health professionals must carefully review available evidence, including witness testimony, medical records, and police reports, to reconstruct the defendant's mental state as accurately as possible⁷⁸.

Courtroom presentation and communication challenges

Presenting complex psychological findings in the courtroom setting creates additional challenges for mental health professionals involved in insanity defense cases⁷⁹. Communicating technical mental concepts and diagnoses to judges, jurors, and legal professionals requires clarity and precision to ensure that legal standards and nuances are properly communicated⁸⁰. Furthermore, mental health experts may face challenges during cross-examination by opposing counsel, who may seek to challenge the credibility or reliability of their assessments. Effective court testimony requires strong communication skills, the ability to withstand tough questioning, and a commitment to maintaining professional integrity and impartiality⁸¹.

Legal standards and variability

One of the primary challenges of the insanity defense is its legal standard, which varies greatly across jurisdictions. Different countries, and sometimes different states within a country, have different criteria for determining insanity. For example, the M'Naghten rule, which originated in English law and is used in various forms in the United States, focuses on cognitive impairment and the ability to distinguish right from wrong. Conversely, the model penal code emphasizes cognitive or volitional impairments affecting behavioral control. This variability leads to inconsistencies in how insanity is defined and assessed, creating challenges for defendants and legal professionals alike. Moreover, public perception and media coverage can influence legal outcomes, further complicating the application of the insanity defense⁸².

Timing of Evaluation:

Generally, a defendant's mental state at the time of a crime cannot be evaluated by an expert until long after the incident has occurred. Memories may fade, and the defendant's mental state at the

⁷⁸ 'Psychiatric Treatment of the Mentally Ill in Prisons and Jails' (PubMed)
<<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/6661569/>> accessed 23 June 2024.

⁷⁹ Alan R Felthous, 'The Insanity Defense: Reflections of the Past and Present' (Oxford Bibliographies)
<<https://www.oxfordbibliographies.com/abstract/document/obo-9780195396607/obo-9780195396607-0198.xml>>
accessed 23 June 2024.

⁸⁰ Margaret E. Bull and others, 'Reported Communication Challenges for Adult Witnesses with Intellectual Disabilities Giving Evidence in Court' (ResearchGate)
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/354456462_Reported_communication_challenges_for_adult_witnesses_with_intellectual_disabilities_giving_evidence_in_court> accessed 23 June 2024.

⁸¹ Celine Chabot-Hanowell, 'Neuroscience in the Courtroom' (Harvard Kennedy School Student Review)
<<https://studentreview.hks.harvard.edu/neuroscience-in-the-courtroom/>> accessed 23 June 2024.

⁸² 'Understanding the Insanity Defense' (McAleer Law) <<https://mcaleerlaw.net/understanding-the-insanitydefense/>>
accessed 23 June 2024.

time of evaluation may differ from their state at the time of the crime⁸³. The time at which a defendant's mental state is evaluated by an expert may affect the accuracy and reliability of an expert's conclusions at trial⁸⁴.

Challenges and Controversies:

The intersection of public perception and legal reform in the insanity defense field is fraught with challenges and debates. Balancing public safety concerns with the rights of persons with mental illness raises moral, ethical, and legal questions about the proper application of the insanity defense. Critics argue that legal reform driven by public opinion may undermine due process rights or perpetuate stigma against individuals with mental health conditions, potentially leading to unjust outcomes or disproportionate punishment⁸⁵.

Underlines the complexities inherent in balancing justice and mental health considerations within the legal system in Bangladesh. The variability of legal standards, procedural complexity, and implications for defendants and the judicial system all contribute to the complex landscape of insanity defense litigation in Bangladesh. By addressing these challenges through legal reforms, improved resources and increased awareness, Bangladesh can strive towards a more equitable and compassionate approach to justice for mentally ill persons involved in the criminal justice system.

6. Case studies of some related issues

- **Steven Steinberg Case⁸⁶⁸⁷** - Steven Steinberg was accused of stabbing his wife 26 times in 1981. The case led to an insanity plea due to Steinberg's claim that he was asleep during the incident. It was Steinberg who called the police, thinking their home had been broken into. Steinberg later did not deny killing his wife but used the argument that he was not responsible because he was asleep and had no memory of killing his wife. The jury found him not guilty because he was temporarily insane at the time of the crime⁸⁸.
- **Lorena Bobbitt Case⁸⁹** – Lorena Bobbitt was acquitted after going to court to have her thenhusband cut off his penis. Bobbitt argued that she had been abused for years and was sexually

⁸³ Mark S. Komrad, 'Psychiatric Treatment of the Mentally Ill in Prisons and Jails' (PubMed) <<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/15048857/>> accessed 23 June 2024.

⁸⁴ Code of Virginia, '§ 19.2-169.5. Determination of Unrestorably Incompetent Defendant's Need for Continued Treatment' (Virginia Law) <<https://law.lis.virginia.gov/vacode/title19.2/chapter11/section19.2-169.5/>> accessed 23 June 2024.

⁸⁵ 'There Have Been Many Controversial' (LawTeacher) <<https://www.lawteacher.net/free-lawessays/criminology/there-have-been-many-controversial-law-essays.php>> accessed 23 June 2024.

⁸⁶ People v. Schmidt, 170 A.D.2d 50 (N.Y. App. Div. 1991)

⁸⁷ N.Y.S.2d 965

⁸⁸ Cornell Law School, 'Insanity Defense' (Legal Information Institute) <https://www.law.cornell.edu/wex/insanity_defense> accessed 23 June 2024.

⁸⁹ Don Pumphrey, 'The Insanity Defense: Most Famous Cases' (Pumphrey Law Firm) <<https://www.pumphreylawfirm.com/blog/insanity-defense-most-famous-cases/>> accessed 23 June 2024.

assaulted by John Bobbitt, which resulted in her having her genitals cut off. The jury found him not guilty by reason of temporary insanity. A judge ordered Bobbitt to undergo a 45-day evaluation period in a psychiatric hospital. After six years of marriage, John and Lorena finalized their divorce.

- **John Hinckley Jr. Case⁹⁰** - John Hinckley was known for attempting to assassinate President Ronald Reagan. During the 1982 trial, experts tried to determine whether he was considered sane at the time of the attempted murder. An objective assessment of his mental state argues that he was a troubled youth. Hinckley Jr. was found not guilty by reason of insanity.

Bangladeshi case

The state Vs Oishee Rahman¹⁰⁴ in this case Oishee Rahman was a teenage girl who killed her father an S.I of police and her mother at night after finishing a night party, after killing her parents she escaped from her house with her younger brother taking valuable ornaments of her mother. She seeks help of her boyfriend who was a drug addict. In this case Oishee plead guilty by giving confessional statement and the lower court sentenced her by death. In lower court circumstance evidence clearly says that Oishee was intoxicated at the time of commission murder of her parents so she was able to claim insanity defense but the defense lawyer never claimed the defense. Subsequently in the appeal stage defense lawyer claim insanity as defense because of at the time of commission of murder oishee was drunk and she was absence of mind, then appeal court seeks opinion from Bangabandhu sheikh mujib medical college and experts ensures that oishee was a drug addict and had mental defect⁹². After satisfied by the statement the jury accepts insanity defense court criticized lower court decision for look after the mental state of the accused and ordered partial defense and oishee get reduced the sentence and sentenced for life imprisonment.

41 CRLJ 711¹⁰⁶ in this case it was held by the apex court that though the court is not bound to accepts the insanity defense claim but if court start to deny such claim without any medical assessment it tends to miscarriage of justice.

15 SCOB 2021(AD) Ataur mridha vs State¹⁰⁷ In this case the appeal division emphasized rules regarding to punishment, if any insane person get partial defense and sentenced for years then it should be proportionate as 1/5. As penal code also validates this proposition.

Sirajul Haque Hawladar Vs Zulekha begum¹⁰⁸ in this case dispute arise from a deed which claimed by the defendant that he was not in his mind when the deed was executed so he claimed that he was insane when the deed was made, bearing all facts and issues in mind the jury finalized that the deed shall be void because the intention of defendant was not to execute the deed.

⁹⁰ Douglas O. Linder, 'The Trial of John Hinckley Jr.' (Famous Trials) <<https://www.famoustrials.com/johnhinckley>> accessed 23 June 2024.

⁹¹ DLR 2016

⁹² 'Oishee Diagnosed with Mental Illness' (The Daily Asian Age)

<<https://dailiasianage.com/news/55711/oisheediagnosed-with-mental-illness>> accessed 23 June 2024.

Dulal Krishna Basu Vs Fakir Ziauddin¹⁰⁹ this case was dismissed on ground of incapacity to institute the suit because of insanity.

In the case of Bheleka Ahmed¹¹⁰, a murder was committed by the accused and he was found not guilty for temporary insane because the killing was not premeditated and there was no quarrel. In this case Calcutta high court divides insanity in five categories-

- Temporary insane
- Emphileptic insanity: The disease is characterized by short transitory of uncontrollable mania followed by complete recovery.
- Somnambulism
- Pherperus insanity: Derived from pregnancy or long time mental disturbance. Occasionally produce a mental condition in which the mind may not be responsible for the acts.
- Drunkenness

In the case of Gedka Goala¹¹¹, in this case the accused had committed several murder when he was suffering from mental defects and the court found in this case that the accused's

- No motive;
- No secrecy;
- No Desire for pre-arrangement; and
- No desires of accomplices, it was held that the accused suffered from unsoundness of mind.

¹⁰⁶ 41 CRLJ 711 ¹⁰⁷ 15 SCOB 2021(AD) ¹⁰⁸ 17 SCOB 2023 HCD ¹⁰⁹ 2 SCOB 2015 HCD ¹¹⁰ 29 cal 493 ¹¹¹ 16 pat 333 (1937)

In the case of Lakshmanan⁹³, where the facts showed that: there was no misunderstanding between the appellant and his wife;(ii) the attack was merciless and it was needless to inflict so many injuries; (iii) such a merciless attack if committed by a sane person would require very strong motives as, so in this case the accused was released for lack of motive and get insanity d

7. Recommendation

Proposed method for determination of insanity:

Bangladesh applies the M Naughton rule in criminal justice where a person can be acquitted if he commits a crime and is incapable of understanding the nature of the crime but criminal liability is not ipso facto meaning that the burden is never shifted or absolved from liability. The United States, Bangladesh, Canada and almost the rest of the world believe in the proposition that criminal liability is never waived so they have implemented the American Law Institute Test In 1953, a group of eminent legal and medical professionals known as the American Law Institute (ALI))

⁹³ CRILJ 110 mad kuttapan 1973

began to study the issue of criminal responsibility⁹⁴. The ALI drafted the Model Penal Code test in 1962 and attempted to address problems with earlier insanity tests⁹⁵. It was designed to implement some psychological advances and avoid causality problems present in the Durham Experiment. The ALI test was seen as a more comprehensive test of insanity than the older M'Naghten test. Compared to M'Naghten, this lowered the standard of insanity from absolute knowledge of right to wrong to a sufficient inability to discern the difference between right and wrong; Thus recognizing degrees of disability. The ALI broadened the insanity test to include a voluntary or "overwhelming impulse" element. The test focuses on "the defendant's understanding of his conduct" and also "the defendant's ability to control his actions"⁹⁶.

Basically, it was a combination of the M'Naghten and Irresistible Impulse tests, just rewritten with different language. By the early 1970s, every federal circuit court except the First and D.C. Circuits had abandoned M'Naghten (either alone or with the irresistible impulse test) and adopted the ALI⁹⁷. The ALI test was seen as a breakthrough and by 1962, it was law in most states and by Oct. 1984, Federal Court Majority Act. Because Hinckley's trial was a federal court adoption of the ALI, it was the subject of the test in this trial. Under the ALI test in federal court, the burden was on the government to prove beyond a reasonable doubt that the defendant was not insane, once sufficient evidence was presented to raise the issue.

Proposal for develop mental health treatment in jail: In Bangladesh there is a legal gap on mental health related issues in jail and there is no law or regulations regarding this matter that's why access to justice on behalf of the prisoners suffering mental defects are very complex, government should enact a proper law or instructions functioning with the jail code and jail authorities also have to be more aware about prisoner rights. On the other hand the apex court can play a vital role on implication of existing laws and requirements.

Integration of the Mental Health Act 2018 into criminal law

It is crucial to more effectively integrate the Mental Health Act 2018 into the criminal justice system to ensure consistent enforcement and protection of mentally ill defendants.

⁹⁴ FindLaw, 'The Model Penal Code Test for Legal Insanity' (FindLaw)

<<https://www.findlaw.com/criminal/criminal-procedure/the-model-penal-code-test-for-legal-insanity.html>> accessed 23 June 2024.

⁹⁵ Merriam-Webster, 'Irresistible Impulse' (Merriam-Webster)

<<https://www.merriamwebster.com/legal/irresistible%20impulse>> accessed 23 June 2024.

⁹⁶ FindLaw, 'The Irresistible Impulse Test' (FindLaw) <<https://www.findlaw.com/criminal/criminal-procedure/theirresistible-impulse-test.html>> accessed 23 June 2024.

⁹⁷ Michael L. Perlin, 'Unpacking the Myths: The American Bar Association's Insanity Defense Recommendations' (1991) 40 Duke LJ 1207

<<https://scholarship.law.duke.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1676&context=dlj>> accessed 23 June 2024.

Improved mental health services in prisons

Increasing the number of mental health professionals and improving facilities in prisons is essential. This can include regular mental health assessments and access to appropriate treatment.

Other recommendations:

- Education and awareness campaigns
Comprehensive education and awareness campaigns need to be implemented to reduce stigma and inform both the public and legal professionals about mental health issues.
- Specialized training programs
Develop specialized training programs for legal and medical professionals to equip them with the skills to appropriately handle mental health issues in criminal justice.
- Establishment of mental health courts
Creating dedicated mental health courts could provide a more nuanced approach to handling cases involving mentally ill defendants, ensuring they receive fair treatment and appropriate care.

8. Conclusion

Mental health issues are widely increasing day by day because of work pressure, heavy use of internet, drugs addiction, relationships, financial conditions and many others physical conditions. Most of foreign country which ensures proper facilities for mentally defects person they also facing rapid cases of mental illness in jail or trial stage, though they have proper rules and regulations regarding this matter they facing challenges but Bangladesh cant creates that environment to ensure the access to justice for person mentally ill. So by Addressing mental health in criminal justice in Bangladesh presents significant challenges, including inadequate legal frameworks, inadequate mental health services, and widespread social stigma. Effective reforms require the integration of the Mental Health Act 2018 into the criminal justice system, improved mental health services in prisons, extensive education and awareness campaigns, specialized training for legal and medical professionals, and the establishment of mental health courts. These measures will build a more equitable legal system, ensuring fair treatment and justice for defendants with mental health conditions.